

CULTURE- BASED PRACTICES: IMPACT ON LEARNING OUTCOMES OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

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ABSTRACT

Culture- Based Practices provides a sense of identity for local communities and residents. This identity shows common values, traditions, and understanding, all central to the proof of identity on strategies of action to improve well-being. In this study, the impact of Culture-Based Practices in the learning outcomes of the students will be tested through assessment of the development in the students learning outcomes despite of the pandemic. This study comprised only one hundred (100) Grade 7 students at Sto. Angel National High School, San Pablo City, Laguna academic year 2020-2021. It was a descriptive design, and random sampling was used. It focuses on the three questions namely: What is the perception of the respondents on the Culture-Based Practices in terms of nationalism, civic competence, values and personal identity; What is the level of achievement of the respondents in Araling Panlipunan in terms of knowledge, comprehension and analysis; and is there a significant relationship between the perceived Culture-Based Practices and the learning outcomes of the respondents in Araling Panlipunan? The following were significant findings of the investigation: The respondents perceive Culture- Based Practices in terms of nationalism (3.80), civic competence (3.49), values (4.15) and personal identity (3.89). The performance of the respondents in the assessment test in Social Studies (Asia 7) in terms of knowledge is 'Excellent' having a grade of 90 and above by 50 or 50% of students; 'Very Good' with a grade of 85-89 by 38 or 38% of the students' in terms of comprehension; and 'Very Good' with a grade of 85-89 by 36 or 36% in terms of analysis. The results show that there is a significant correlation between the Culture-Based Practices and the learning outcomes of the students and Culture-Based Practices such as Nationalism, Civic Competence, Values and Personal Identity are not predictors of students' achievement in Araling Panlipunan. is not supported by evidence; hence, it is not sustained. This means that the more the respondents are practicing their Culture-Based Practices its effect on learning outcomes also increases. Students learned that cultural practices will lead to progression of the society and him.

Keywords: Culture-Based Practices and Learning Outcomes